

Mathematical Geosciences

Enhancing Geostatistical Analysis of Natural Resources Data with Complex Spatial Formations through non-Euclidean Distances

--Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	MATG-D-24-00163	
Full Title:	Enhancing Geostatistical Analysis of Natural Resources Data with Complex Spatial Formations through non-Euclidean Distances	
Article Type:	S.I. : GeoENV2024	
Keywords:	geostatistics; covariance models; non-Euclidean distance; MLE; Gaussian anamorhposis	
Corresponding Author:	Emmanouil Varouchakis Technical University of Crete: Polytechnio Kretes CHANIA, GREECE	
Corresponding Author Secondary Information:		
Corresponding Author's Institution:	Technical University of Crete: Polytechnio Kretes	
Corresponding Author's Secondary Institution:		
First Author:	Maria Despoina Koltsidopoulou, M.Sc.	
First Author Secondary Information:		
Order of Authors:	Maria Despoina Koltsidopoulou, M.Sc.	
	ANDREAS PAVLIDES, Ph.D	
	Dionissios T. Hristopulos, PhD	
	Emmanouil A. Varouchakis, PhD	
Order of Authors Secondary Information:		
Funding Information:	Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (16537)	Prof. Emmanouil A. Varouchakis
Abstract:	<p>In geostatistical modeling, traditional covariance models based on Euclidean distance often fail in complex geographic environments, especially when natural barriers or irregular terrain distort spatial relationships. This study explores the use of non-Euclidean distance metrics, such as Manhattan, Minkowski, and Chebyshev distances, to improve the accuracy of spatial covariance models in such environments. We apply several covariance models -Exponential, Gaussian, Spherical, Spartan Spatial Random Field (SSRF), and the recently developed Harmonic Covariance Estimation (HCE) model- to estimate soil aluminium concentration data from a region with complex physical barriers. Gaussian Anamorphosis with the new Kernel Cumulative Density Estimator (KCDE) was used to normalize the data. The model parameters for all covariance models and all distances were estimated via maximum likelihood estimation (MLE).</p> <p>The models were tested for their applicability in non-Euclidean distances by calculating the Eigenvalues of the resulting covariance matrices, in order to ensure positive-definiteness.</p> <p>In this case study, the Gaussian and Spherical Models were found to be inadequate for non-Euclidean spaces as the covariance matrices were not positive-definite. On the other hand, the SSRF, Exponential, and HCE models provided valid covariance matrices consistently. In particular, the HCE model outperformed the others in all distance metrics demonstrating the robustness and adaptability of HCE in a non-Euclidean geostatistical environment.</p>	

[Click here to view linked References](#)

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Enhancing Geostatistical Analysis of Natural Resources Data with Complex Spatial Formations through non-Euclidean Distances

Maria Despoina Koltsidopoulou¹, Andrew Pavlides²,
Dionissios T. Hristopoulos¹, Emmanouil A. Varouchakis^{2*}

¹School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Technical University of Crete, Chania, 73100, Crete, Greece.

²School of Mineral Resources Engineering, Technical University of Crete, Chania, 73100, Crete, Greece.

*Corresponding author. E-mail: evarouchakis@tuc.gr;

Abstract

In geostatistical modeling, traditional covariance models based on Euclidean distance often fail in complex geographic environments, especially when natural barriers or irregular terrain distort spatial relationships. This study explores the use of non-Euclidean distance metrics, such as Manhattan, Minkowski, and Chebyshev distances, to improve the accuracy of spatial covariance models in such environments. We apply several covariance models -Exponential, Gaussian, Spherical, Spartan Spatial Random Field (SSRF), and the recently developed Harmonic Covariance Estimation (HCE) model- to estimate soil aluminium concentration data from a region with complex physical barriers. Gaussian Anamorphosis with the new Kernel Cumulative Density Estimator (KCDE) was used to normalize the data. The model parameters for all covariance models and all distances were estimated via maximum likelihood estimation (MLE). The models were tested for their applicability in non-Euclidean distances by calculating the Eigenvalues of the resulting covariance matrices, in order to ensure positive-definiteness. In this case study, the Gaussian and Spherical Models were found to be inadequate for non-Euclidean spaces as the covariance matrices were not positive-definite. On the other hand, the SSRF, Exponential, and HCE models provided valid covariance matrices consistently. In particular, the HCE model outperformed the others in all distance metrics demonstrating the robustness and adaptability of HCE in a non-Euclidean geostatistical environment.

Keywords: geostatistics, covariance models, non-Euclidean distance, MLE, Gaussian anamorhposis

1 Introduction

Traditional covariance models based on Euclidean metrics are likely to fail in complex geographical environments. For instance, spatial relationships are distorted by physical barriers such as faults through which the deposition of natural resources can be disturbed. Standard models based on non-Euclidean distance metrics usually lead to inaccuracies of resources and the reason is these disturbances. Addressing these challenges can occur by incorporating non-Euclidean distance metrics, such as Manhattan or Chebyshev distances, through which more robust and flexible options are provided for analyzing complex geographic domains. This approach therefore increases the possibility of more accurate modelling and improved resource management.

However, while traditional covariance models are based on Euclidean distances and are designed to produce positive-definite covariance matrices, they can fail when applied to non-Euclidean spaces. Consequently, we are led to inaccurate statistical analysis and prediction as positive definiteness leads to the invertibility of a covariance matrix. To address such challenges, the development of new covariance models that can be adapted to non-Euclidean measures arises. A necessary condition is that the covariance matrix remains positively definite.

The study of traditional geostatistical models based on Euclidean distances contains some limitations; in his paper, Frank C. Curriero (2006) advocates using non-Euclidean metrics in cases where physical barriers distort spatial relationships. After analysis and simulations, he concludes that non-Euclidean distances can significantly improve prediction accuracy in complex geographic environments such as river networks and irregular terrains. In particular [1], he explains how eigenvalues can be used to test whether a covariance matrix with non-Euclidean distances is positive-definite, showing that the exponential model leads to permissible matrices for certain non-Euclidean distances. This approach is further documented in the research conducted by Theodoridou et al. (2017), where the application of Euclidean distance metrics, such as that of Manhattan, was shown to improve the exact prediction in spatial geostatistical analyses [2].

Building on this, the study by BJK Davis et al. (2019) presents a new method to enhance the validity and accuracy of spatial covariance structures based initially on non-Euclidean metrics in geostatistical models. Through simulations and real-world applications, such as water quality assessments in the Chesapeake Bay, this method improves geostatistical predictions [3].

Further research has been carried out by Hristopulos (2023) who introduced advanced methodologies to develop non-separable covariance kernels in Gaussian spatio-temporal processes using a hybrid spectral method. The method is inspired by physical systems as well as the linear damped harmonic oscillator (LDHO) model. More specifically, the model is one that simulates the back and forth motion of a

1 system (such as a spring or a pendulum) where a restoring force is compensated by
2 a damping force (such as friction or air resistance). This approach allows kernels to
3 incorporate monotonic and oscillatory damping into their spacetime correlations. The
4 use of the stochastic LDHO model to construct spatio-temporal covariance kernels
5 improves existing models leading to higher prediction accuracy for data governed by
6 non-Euclidean processes. These developments highlight the potential of non-Euclidean
7 approaches to better identify spatial relationships in data in complex systems [4].

8 Further studies have explored in depth the application of non-Euclidean metrics in
9 geostatistical modeling to address complex spatio-temporal relationships, such as Agou
10 et al. (2019) who demonstrated the use of kriging regression on the island of Crete to
11 analyze rainfall data from a sparse network of monitoring stations. In their research,
12 they were led to anisotropic spatial correlations through the integration of topographic
13 data and Spartan variogram function [5]. On similar lines, Varouchakis et al. (2022)
14 used spatiotemporal geostatistical analysis to quantify groundwater level variations,
15 demonstrating that incorporating the Manhattan distance metric led to a significant
16 improvement in model accuracy in regions with complex geological features [6]. In
17 addition to these, Ver Hoef et al. (2018) developed a reduced-degree predictive process
18 model that constructs valid spatial covariance tables. In the process, they addressed
19 the challenges of implementing kriging models with non-Euclidean distances [7].

20 The main objective of this study is to investigate existing models and develop a
21 new covariance model that can be reliably used with non-Euclidean distance metrics to
22 improve spatial analysis and resource estimation in complex geographic environments.
23 Focusing on Manhattan and different implementations of Minkowski and Chebyshev
24 distances, our work will explore how these metrics can be incorporated into geo-
25 statistical models to provide more accurate and realistic representations of spatial
26 relationships and a comparison of the different models tested. The scope includes the
27 application of the methods to real data of aluminium soil concentration originally
28 taken for a geochemical analysis. Gaussian anamorphosis was deemed necessary. This
29 anamorphosis was performed with a novel method based on the Cumulative Den-
30 sity Function, not the Probability Density Function, and is called Kernel Cumulative
31 Density Estimator (KCDE).

32 2 Methodology

33
34
35
36 The spatial distribution of variables is used utilizing the mathematical framework of
37 random fields [8–10]. A scalar random field $X(\mathbf{s})$ where $\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ represents the position
38 vector, is defined as a random function $\mathcal{D} \subset \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, where \mathcal{D} is the spatial domain.
39 This random field is characterized by n -point joint probability density functions, where
40 $n = 1, 2, \dots$ denotes a positive integer. The data, represented by the sampling regions
41 $\{\mathbf{s}_1, \dots, \mathbf{s}_N\}$ and the corresponding values of the random variables $\{x_1, \dots, x_N\}$ are
42 considered as partial samples of the random field.

43 The field is reconstructed into a rectangular map grid \mathbb{G} consisting of points
44 $\{\mathbf{z}_1, \dots, \mathbf{z}_P\}$. The estimation points will be denoted in general by $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^d$, with esti-
45 mation points $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{G}$. The random fields are decomposed into a deterministic part
46 (trend) and a stochastic part (fluctuation) as follows:
47
48

$$X(\mathbf{s}) = m_x(\mathbf{s}) + X'(\mathbf{s}) \quad (1)$$

The function $m_x(\mathbf{s})$ is the trend. It represents the mathematical expectation of the random field, $\mathbb{E}[X(\mathbf{s})]$ and it is often modeled as a low-degree polynomial.

The fluctuation $X'(\mathbf{s})$ represents the stochastic component of $X(\mathbf{s})$. It is obtained by subtracting the trend from $X(\mathbf{s})$ and thus is equal to the residuals of the field [11].

2.1 Distance Measures

In this work, various distances are examined and explored along with the covariance models.

Euclidean distance:

Euclidean distance is the most commonly used form of distance and represents the actual distance in our world. It calculates the straight-line distance between two points $\mathbf{P} = (p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n)$ and $\mathbf{Q} = (q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n)$ in an n -dimensional space using the formula:

$$d_{\text{Euclidean}}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Q}) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (p_i - q_i)^2}, \quad (2)$$

Manhattan Distance:

Manhattan distance (also known as *taxicab* or *city block*), measures the distance between two points by summing the absolute differences in their coordinates, as shown in:

$$d_{\text{Manhattan}}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Q}) = \sum_{i=1}^n |p_i - q_i| \quad (3)$$

This distance measure is most applicable in cases where traffic or paths are confined to a grid. Typically this is the case with fluids passing through a porous material or water in rivers.

Minkowski distance:

The Minkowski distance provides a generalized framework for measuring distance in multidimensional spaces via the parameter k . This distance can express both the Euclidean distance (for $k = 2$) and Manhattan distance (for $k = 1$) as special cases. The Minkowski distance between points \mathbf{P} and \mathbf{Q} is defined as:

$$d_{\text{Minkowski}}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Q}) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n |p_i - q_i|^k \right)^{1/k}. \quad (4)$$

Chebyshev distance:

The Chebyshev distance (also known as *chessboard distance*) calculates the maximum difference between the coordinates of two points along any dimension. The equation

for the Chebyshev distance between points \mathbf{P} and \mathbf{Q} is expressed as follows:

$$d_{\text{Chebyshev}}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Q}) = \max_i (|p_i - q_i|) \quad (5)$$

This distance measure is employed in scenarios where only the highest difference in any dimension matters, such as in specific optimization problems or game strategies. In particular, Fig. 1 presents an illustrative example of the two-dimensional distance for three different distance measures, between the point $\mathbf{P} = (0, 0)$ (origin) and points $\mathbf{Q}_i = (q_{i,1}, q_{i,2})$, $i = 1, \dots, 9$.

2	$\sqrt{5}$	$2\sqrt{2}$	2	2	2	2	3	4
1	$\sqrt{2}$	$\sqrt{5}$	1	1	2	1	2	3
0	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	2
(a) Euclidean			(b) Chebyshev			(c) Manhattan		

Fig. 1: An example of the various distances in a two-dimensional space between point $\mathbf{P} = (0, 0)$ and points $\mathbf{Q}_i = (q_{i,1}, q_{i,2}) = (\{0, 1, 2, 0, 1, 2, 0, 1, 2\}, \{0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 2\})$.

2.2 Gaussian Anamorphosis

Gaussianity is desirable in the estimation of random fields. Various studies have shown that linear predictors perform better if the underlying distribution is close to the normal distribution [11–13].

This research uses a kernel-based (non-parametric) data-driven approach to conduct Gaussian anamorphosis [12, 14], KCDE. Unlike other non-parametric methods that focus on probability density, this method directly targets the Cumulative Density Function (CDF) with explicit density integration. This method has been described in detail [15], but a summary of the process is provided here.

Let $\{x_{[i]}\}_{i=1}^N$ represent the ordered sample of data values. Then, the non-parametric, *kernel-based estimate of the CDF* (KCDE), $\hat{F}_K(\cdot)$, can be obtained from the following weighted sum [12]:

$$\hat{F}_K(x) = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{N} \tilde{K} \left(\frac{x - x_{[i]}}{b} \right) \quad (6)$$

where $\tilde{K}(\cdot)$ corresponds to *CDF kernel step* which is defined via the integral [10, 16]:

$$\tilde{K}\left(\frac{x - x_{[i]}}{b}\right) = \frac{1}{b} \int_{-\infty}^x K\left(\frac{x' - x_{[i]}}{b}\right) dx', \quad (7)$$

where K is the chosen Kernel function, where in this case study is the triweight kernel [16].

Consequently, in the following implementation, the Gaussian anamorphosis is performed on the fluctuation $X'(\mathbf{s})$ (i.e. after the trend is removed) using KCDE in combination with the normal-effects transformation method [17], as explained in [15]. In addition, a *look-up* table was used in combination with the normal score transformation and KCDE to perform the anamorphosis.

2.3 Covariance Functions

The models attempting to represent spatial processes rely on the spatial correlations between the data. These correlations are reflected in the covariance function that characterizes the random field:

$$c_X(\mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{s}_2) = \mathbb{E}[X(\mathbf{s}_1)X(\mathbf{s}_2)] - \mathbb{E}[X(\mathbf{s}_1)]\mathbb{E}[X(\mathbf{s}_2)] \quad (8)$$

The covariance function is fundamental in exploring the spatial or spatiotemporal relationships within the values of the investigated random field, as it quantifies how values at different locations co-vary [18]. However, not all functions can be used as a covariance function. For a function to be permissible as a covariance model, it should satisfy specific mathematical conditions. For Euclidean distances, adherence to the conditions set by the Bochner Theorem [19] ensures that the function is a valid covariance function and thus, it will result in a positive-definite covariance matrix.

When dealing with non-Euclidean distances the more generic *Cramér* extends the applicability of covariance functions to non-Euclidean spaces and thus, consistent with the underlying geometry of such spaces [20, 21].

Commonly used theoretical covariance models include the exponential, Gaussian, and spherical models [22]. The equations for these models are provided below, where σ_X^2 represents the variance, $\|\mathbf{r}\|$ denotes the Euclidean norm of the lag vector \mathbf{r} , and ξ is the correlation length.

Exponential

$$c_x(r) = \sigma_x^2 [\exp(-\|\mathbf{r}\|/\xi)]. \quad (9)$$

Gaussian

$$c_x(r) = \sigma_x^2 [\exp(-\|\mathbf{r}\|^2/\xi^2)]. \quad (10)$$

Spherical

$$c_x(r) = \begin{cases} \sigma_x^2 \left[1 - 1.5 \left(\frac{\|\mathbf{r}\|}{\xi} \right) + 0.5 \left(\frac{\|\mathbf{r}\|}{\xi} \right)^3 \right] & \text{if } \|\mathbf{r}\| \leq \xi \\ 0 & \text{if } \|\mathbf{r}\| \geq \xi. \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

2.3.1 Spartan spatial random field model

Spartan Spatial Random Fields (SSRFs) are a family of geostatistical models [23]. The case of covariance SSRFs is provided, where a Spartan-specific probability density (PDF) with spatial dependence derived from generalized gradient and Laplacian operators is used. The PDF of the SSRF depends on a small set of parameters, allowing modeling of spatial processes with controlled roughness and differentiability [24].

In three spatial dimensions, the SSRF model is given by [25, 26]:

$$C(\mathbf{r}) = \begin{cases} \frac{\eta_0}{2\pi\Delta} \mathbb{E}^{-\frac{|\mathbf{r}|}{\xi}} \beta_2 \left(\frac{\sin(\frac{|\mathbf{r}|}{\xi} \beta_1)}{\frac{|\mathbf{r}|}{\xi}} \right) & |\eta_1| < 2, \\ \frac{\eta_0}{8\pi} \mathbb{E}^{-\frac{|\mathbf{r}|}{\xi}} & \eta_1 = 2, \\ \frac{\eta_0}{4\pi\Delta} \left(\mathbb{E}^{-\frac{|\mathbf{r}|}{\xi}} \omega_1 - \mathbb{E}^{-\frac{|\mathbf{r}|}{\xi}} \omega_2 \right) \frac{1}{(\omega_1 - \omega_2) \frac{|\mathbf{r}|}{\xi}} & \eta_1 > 2. \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

In equation (12), η_0 is the scale factor that determines the magnitude of the fluctuations, η_1 is the rigidity coefficient that controls the shape of the covariance function, and ξ is the characteristic length that determines the range of spatial correlations and normalizes the distance. The additional coefficients are defined as $\beta_{1,2} = |2 \mp \eta_1|^{1/2}$, $\omega_{1,2} = \left(\frac{\eta_1 \mp \Delta}{2} \right)^{1/2}$, and $\Delta = |\eta_1^2 - 4|^{1/2}$. The correlation length in the SSRF model is influenced by both η_1 and ξ . Notably, when $\eta_1 = 2$, the Spartan covariance simplifies to the exponential model [25]. SSRF models are differentiable, a property that is useful for applications where smoothness of the spatial field is important.

The SSRF model has performed well in various interpolation studies, such as those involving radioactivity dose rates [23], coal reserves estimation [11], and groundwater level modeling [27]. Furthermore, it has been proven to always give positive-definite covariance matrices for the Manhattan distance [6].

2.3.2 Covariance in non-Euclidean distances

An investigation of the validity of covariance models using non-Euclidean distance metrics was carried out through the study of Curriero et al. (2006) and internally developed code (MATLAB 23a) [1]. This investigation aimed to clarify how different spatial metrics, specifically Manhattan distance, affect the validity and performance of different covariance models. The findings indicated that, unlike Gaussian, spherical, and various forms of the Matérn class, the exponential covariance function returns admissible, positively definite covariance matrices with Manhattan distance.

Further analysis by [6] revealed that the Spartan Spatial Random Field (SSRF) model, which shares structural similarities with the exponential covariance function, also produces valid spatiotemporal covariance structures when the Manhattan distance is used [25, 26]. Therefore, the SSRF covariance has guaranteed consistency for the Manhattan distance. Consequently, the Spartan model is acceptable at certain non-Euclidean distances, which conclusion was supported in a further analysis through the application of the assumption of Curriero et al. (2006) [1]. The results confirmed that the eigenvalues of the covariance matrix derived from the Spartan model are positive, thus ensuring that the covariance matrix remains positively definite.

Covariance models, such as those of spherical and Gaussian models, do not always produce permissible, positive-definite covariance matrices for non-Euclidean distances. In certain cases, covariances may result in a permissible matrix, which may not be sufficient. There have been several examples in the bibliography where these models could not form a positive definite matrix [1, 3, 6].

2.4 HCE: Covariance model based on LDHO

In [28], the Linearly Damped Harmonic Oscillator (LDHO) leads to the following spatiotemporal covariance function:

$$C(r, \tau) = \frac{\sigma_0^2}{(2\pi)^{d/2} r^\nu} \int_0^\infty k^{d/2} J_\nu(kr) A(k) e^{-|\tau|B(k)/\tau_c} dk, \quad (13)$$

where r represents the spatial distance and τ denotes the temporal lag. The parameter σ_0^2 is the variance of the process, and d indicates the spatial dimension. The term ν is the order of the Bessel function $J_\nu(kr)$, with $J_\nu(kr)$ being the Bessel function of the first kind of order $\nu = d/2 - 1$. The functions $A(k)$ and $B(k)$ define the dependencies on spatial frequency, and τ_c is the characteristic timescale governing the temporal decay.

Different functional forms of $A(k)$ and $B(k)$ yield permissible covariance functions under the Bochner Theorem, which produce positive definite matrices under Euclidean distance.

To adapt the LDHO model to non-Euclidean distances, we consider an alternative parametrization where $A(k) = \exp(-\beta k)$ and $B(k) = \alpha + \xi k$ with α, β being model parameters and ξ the correlation length. Substituting these into Eq. 13, the covariance function turns into:

$$C(r, \tau) = \frac{\sigma_0^2 e^{-a|\tau|/\tau_c}}{(2\pi)^{d/2} r^\nu} \int_0^\infty k^{\nu+1} J_\nu(kr) e^{-k(\beta + \xi|\tau|/\tau_c)} dk. \quad (14)$$

After performing the integration, the resulting spatiotemporal covariance function is:

$$C(r, \tau) = \frac{\sigma_0^2 \Gamma\left(\frac{d+1}{2}\right)}{\pi^{\frac{d+1}{2}} \tilde{\tau}_c} (\beta \tilde{\tau}_c + \xi |\tau|) e^{-a|\tau|/\tilde{\tau}_c} \left[r^2 + \left(\beta + \frac{\xi |\tau|}{\tilde{\tau}_c} \right)^2 \right]^{-\frac{d+1}{2}}. \quad (15)$$

For the spatial marginal covariance, assuming isotropy, we obtain the covariance function (referred to as Harmonic Covariance Estimation, *HCE*):

$$C_{\text{HCE}}(r) = \frac{\sigma_0^2 \Gamma\left(\frac{d+1}{2}\right) \beta}{\pi^{\frac{d+1}{2}} (r^2 + \beta^2)^{\frac{d+1}{2}}} \quad (16)$$

This *HCE* covariance function is permissible in Euclidean space. We applied Curriero's et al. (2006) [1] method to test the eigenvalues of the covariance matrices derived from under non-Euclidean distances. The matrices remained positive-definite, ensuring their invertibility and applicability in kriging predictions.

In Fig. 2, we present a visual comparison of three key covariance functions: the HCE from Eq. (16), the Spherical model, and the Exponential model. This comparison

Fig. 2: Comparative Analysis of Spatial Covariance Functions

is theoretical, with both the sill and range set to 1, making them unitless in this example. Similar to the Exponential model, the HCE tends to 0 with increased distance as it's not a compact support model. The similarities extend further; as shown, the HCE decreases slower than the Exponential model at short distances, and even more, than the Spherical model at very short distances. However, over time, it tends to 0 approximately at the same rate as the Exponential model.

2.5 Maximum Likelihood Estimation

To estimate the parameters of the tested models, we used maximum likelihood estimation (MLE), which is a statistical method for estimating parameters that are less sensitive to the model and more robust than those obtained by fitting the variogram [10].

For set of spatial data points $z(\mathbf{s}_1), z(\mathbf{s}_2), \dots, z(\mathbf{s}_n)$, where $z(\mathbf{s}_i)$ represents the value at location \mathbf{s}_i , the likelihood function for the parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ of a spatial model can be defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{z}) = \prod_{i=1}^n f(z(\mathbf{s}_i); \boldsymbol{\theta}) \quad (17)$$

Where $f(z(\mathbf{s}_i); \boldsymbol{\theta})$ is the probability density function (PDF) at location \mathbf{s}_i with parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$.

The goal of MLE is to find the parameter values $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ that maximize the likelihood function. It is often more convenient to work with the log-likelihood function:

$$\ell(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{z}) = \log \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{z}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \log f(z(\mathbf{s}_i); \boldsymbol{\theta}) \quad (18)$$

Maximizing the log-likelihood function is mathematically equivalent to maximizing the likelihood function. In geostatistics, the covariance function parameters, such as the range, sill, and nugget, are typically estimated using MLE. These estimates are fundamental in characterizing spatial dependence and facilitating spatial prediction and interpolation.

2.6 Ordinary Kriging

The Kriging method, a geostatistical interpolation method used for spatial prediction and mapping, provides the best linear unbiased estimate (BLUE) of a random field at unsampled locations based on observed values from nearby points [29]. The predicted value at a study point \mathbf{u} is obtained from a weighted linear combination of the values of neighboring points, with weights determined by minimizing the variance of the error ϵ using the covariance matrix or the variogram [8, 30].

For Ordinary Kriging (OK), the prediction of the field at the study point \mathbf{u} is expressed by the linear combination shown in Equation (19).

$$\hat{X}(\mathbf{u}) = \sum_{\alpha=1}^{n(\mathbf{u})} \lambda_{\alpha} X(\mathbf{s}_{\alpha}) \quad (19)$$

where λ_{α} refers to the Kriging linear weights ($\sum_{i=1}^{n(\mathbf{u})} \lambda_i = 1$). The weights are calculated with the help of the augmented covariance or variogram matrix C_X from Eq. (20)

$$C_X(\mathbf{s})\Lambda = C_X(\mathbf{u}), \quad (20)$$

with $\Lambda = \{\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_{n(\mathbf{u})}, \mu\}^T$, μ being the lagrange coefficient and $C_X(\mathbf{s}), C_X(\mathbf{u})$ the augmented variogram or covariance matrices.

A neighborhood $\omega(\mathbf{u})$ is often employed in Kriging, which includes $n(\mathbf{u}) \leq N$ points from $\mathbf{s}_i (i = 1, \dots, N)$ around the prediction point \mathbf{u} . The size of this neighborhood is determined by the range h of the variogram, as data outside $\omega(\mathbf{u})$ are considered uncorrelated with the value of $X(\mathbf{u})$.

One key advantage of Kriging over deterministic methods is its ability to calculate the variance of the prediction error, σ_{OK}^2 . In the case of ordinary Kriging (OK), if the data are normally distributed, this variance corresponds to a normal distribution of values around the predicted value [10, 31, 32]. The variance for OK is given by:

$$\sigma_{\text{OK}}^2(\mathbf{u}) = \sum_{i=1}^{n(\mathbf{u})} \lambda_i \gamma_X(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{s}_i) - \mu. \quad (21)$$

In this study, OK is used, which assumes that the trend is an unknown constant within the neighborhood [13].

3 Case Study

This research used soil aluminium concentration data from an area with complex physical barriers (elevation differences, private property, etc.) that make physical access and sampling difficult. Due to the difficult terrain, we were guided to the sampling pattern shown in Fig. 3a. This atypical sampling pattern provides an opportunity to investigate the ability of non-Euclidean metrics to capture the spatial dependencies of Al concentration better than Euclidean metrics.

Preliminary analysis showed no significant evidence of a trend in the data, with the correlation coefficient between trend and data being below $\rho = 0.25$. Consequently, the trend was not removed, resulting in using OK instead. The data does not follow the normal distribution, which complicates the prediction. Following, KCDE was used to perform the Gaussian anamorphosis on the fluctuation data of the soil aluminium concentration. The data before and after the transformation are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary Statistics of Aluminium Concentration in soil, before and after Gaussian Anamorphosis.

Statistic	Normalized Value	Value (ppm)
Minimum	-1.9758	0.0
Maximum	2.6574	76280
Mean	0.0120	3243.8
Median	-0.0414	1020
Standard Deviation	0.9673	8668.5

Fig. 3: Data Visualization: (a) Sampling points by location, and (b) Normal probability plot of the transformed aluminium concentration data.

The concentration of Al in the soil peaks to very high values, which is to be expected. Moreover, the normal probability plot in Fig. 3b shows that KCDE performed sufficiently and the distribution of Al data is close to the normal distribution.

4 Results & Discussion

In this study, several covariance models were examined: Exponential, Gaussian, Spherical, SSRF, and HCE. The distance metrics employed were Euclidean, Manhattan, Chebyshev, and the Minkowski distance with exponent $k = 2/3, k = 1.5$. The covariance model parameters for all distance metrics were estimated using MLE (see section 2.5) using soil Al concentration from a geochemical study, after Gaussian anamorphosis.

Indicative examples of variograms for different distances are shown in Fig. 4. It should be noted that the variograms are presented just for illustration purposes only, while the model parameters are estimated with MLE. The experimental variograms differ for each distance metric.

(a) Exponential-Minkowski, $k = 1.5$

(b) HCE-Euclidean

(c) SSRF-Minkowski, $k = 2/3$

(d) HCE-Chebyshev

Fig. 4: Variogram fitting for different models and distances. The parameters are estimated with MLE. Distance in km.

We first evaluated the suitability of covariance matrices derived from non-Euclidean distances to investigate the performance of different covariance models with different distance metrics. This was done by calculating their eigenvalues, as suggested by [1, 2]. The eigenvalues for the covariance matrices of the sampling data were calculated and it was found that the SSRF, Exponential, and HCE models yield positive-definite matrices. The Gaussian and Spherical covariance models failed to produce permissible, positive-definite covariance matrices for any distance other than Euclidean.

Focusing on the models that produced covariance matrices with permissible eigenvalues, we continued the analysis by using these for OK on a prediction grid with a 100m x 100m cell size. After prediction, the estimated values at grid locations were converted to *ppm* using the *look-up* table (see Sec. 2.2). Leave-one-out-cross-validation (LCV) was employed to compare the performance of the various models for the different distance metrics. The validation metrics obtained from these tests are presented in Table 2 below. All analyses were conducted using custom code developed in MATLAB 23a.

Table 2: Validation Measures after Back Transformation: Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Pearson’s correlation coefficient (Rho), and Mean Error (ME)

Model	Distance	MAE	RMSE	Rho	ME
Exponential	Manhattan	1972.44	6252.29	0.68801	-600.09
Exponential	Euclidean	1974.02	6256.27	0.68754	-600.83
Exponential	Minkowski, $k=2/3$	1974.73	6242.55	0.68920	-597.32
Exponential	Minkowski, $k=1.5$	1973.18	6255.21	0.68766	-600.89
Exponential	Chebyshev	1977.59	6261.62	0.68692	-604.52
SSRF	Manhattan	2473.48	6334.43	0.69168	-308.63
SSRF	Euclidean	2946.26	9159.92	0.49017	368.57
SSRF	Minkowski, $k=2/3$	4126.81	12284.10	0.32047	1273.46
SSRF	Minkowski, $k=1.5$	3188.22	9750.24	0.45928	654.42
SSRF	Chebyshev	3156.27	9591.26	0.46817	624.89
HCE	Manhattan	1894.12	5609.39	0.75862	-537.26
HCE	Euclidean	1897.91	5610.54	0.75851	-539.06
HCE	Minkowski, $k=2/3$	1890.10	5609.53	0.75862	-536.00
HCE	Minkowski, $k=1.5$	1896.31	5609.77	0.75858	-538.09
HCE	Chebyshev	1902.13	5613.44	0.75823	-541.08

The Exponential model demonstrates consistent performance across all distance metrics, with only minor variations in MAE, RMSE, Rho, and ME. The Manhattan and Minkowski ($k = 2/3$) distances yield slightly better results, exhibiting lower RMSE and higher Rho compared to the Euclidean and Chebyshev distances, but the improvement of those distance metrics is not statistically significant.

In contrast, the SSRF model underperforms relative to the Exponential model, showing significantly higher errors (MAE and RMSE) and lower correlations (Rho) across most distance metrics. The model’s performance is particularly poor with the Minkowski ($k = 2/3$) distance, where it records the highest RMSE and lowest Rho values. However, the Manhattan distance shows relatively better results for the SSRF

1 model, recording higher Rho and lower MAE and RMSE compared to other distance
 2 metrics. In general, the SSRF is considered to have the worst performance from the
 3 models tested for this dataset. However, this is the result of the MLE parameters
 4 for the model and the SSRF produced permissible matrices for all distance metrics
 5 regardless.

6 The HCE model outperforms both the Exponential and SSRF models across all
 7 distance metrics, consistently achieving the lowest MAE and RMSE values across all
 8 distance metrics. Rho is the highest among all models. The differences between the
 9 various distances are minimal, but the Manhattan distance yields the best perfor-
 10 mance, while the Chebyshev distance, though still effective, shows the least favorable
 11 outcomes. The results for the HCE are encouraging, indicating it can be a reliable
 12 option for spatial modeling across non-Euclidean distance metrics.

13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27 (a) Exponential-Minkowski, $k = 1.5$

28 (b) HCE-Euclidean

29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42 (c) HCE-Chebyshev

43
44 **Fig. 5:** Kriging plots for concentration of Al (ppm), Exponential & HCE model using
 45 different distance metrics: (a) Minkowski, $k = 1.5$; (b) Euclidean; and (c) Chebyshev.
 46 Distances are in km.

1 It is not uncommon for the back-transform of predictions to include bias [15, 17].
2 This is also the case in our study, with the bias (ME) being significant compared to
3 the range of the original data. One reason for the bias is that when the symmetric
4 predictions are back transformed to the original, skewed distribution, the kriging pre-
5 dictors are aligned with the median of the prediction’s distribution rather than the
6 forecast distribution’s mean. Another factor that increases the mean error is that the
7 highest value (76280 ppm) is significantly higher than the Al concentration at the sur-
8 rounding sampling locations. Thus, the LCV that works by subtracting a point and
9 predicting the value at that location is disadvantaged when trying to predict the value
10 at that location, as the actual value is an outlier.

11 Some example Kriging maps for HCE and Exponential covariance are shown in
12 Fig. 5. The Kriging search neighborhood depends on the estimated correlation range
13 (i.e. range of influence) and is therefore different for each distance and covariance
14 model.

15 It is shown in Fig. 5 that all displayed covariance models and distance metrics
16 effectively capture the spatial variability of the field. All figures indicate the high
17 concentration at the northwestern edge with a small area of high concentration about
18 3 km east and 4 km north. Low values are captured in the northeastern part in all
19 cases. The similarities between the kriging maps are expected, considering that both
20 Exponential and HCE yielded similarly well-performed LCV results.

22 5 Conclusions

23 In this study, we tested various covariance models; the Gaussian, Exponential, Spheri-
24 cal, SSRF and the recently developed HCE model with non-Euclidean distance metrics
25 for aluminium concentration in soil data. Sampling was informal and focused on a few
26 easily accessible areas, effectively removing much of the field without sampling. Data
27 were normalized using KCDE Gaussian anamorphosis with a *look-up* table. The nor-
28 mal probability plot revealed that the transformed data were closely matched to the
29 normal distribution.

30 Using the normalized data, MLE was employed to estimate the parameters of
31 the different tested models for various distance metrics. The metrics tested were
32 Euclidean, Manhattan distance, Chebyshev distance and the Minkowski distance
33 with $k = 2/3, k = 1.5$. The eigenvalues of the resulting covariance matrices were
34 calculated. The Gaussian and Spherical models failed to produce positive-definite
35 covariance matrices for non-Gaussian distance metrics and were therefore omitted. The
36 SSRF, Exponential and HCE covariance matrices were positive-definite all distances
37 investigated and could therefore be used for kriging predictions.

38 We used these covariance models to perform OK on a grid with a cell size of 100m x
39 100m. While all three models were able to provide predictions, the validation measures
40 were better for HCE, satisfactory for Exponential, and SSRF underperformed with
41 the exception of Manhattan distance. For both the HCE and the Exponential model,
42 the various distances returned similar validation measures. HCE had RMSEs from
43 5609 ppm to 5613 ppm with $\rho = 0.758$ to $\rho = 0.759$. Validation measures for the
44 Exponential covariance also had a small range with RMSEs from 6243 ppm to 6261
45

1 ppm with $\rho = 0.687$ to $\rho = 0.689$. Thus, while using non-Euclidean distances did
2 not significantly improve the predictions in this case, HCE performed well and the
3 non-Euclidean distance metrics were competitive.

4 The bias in the back-transformation for all distances was minor compared to the
5 range of data values (0-76280 ppm), but noticeable (in the range of -540 ppm to -605
6 ppm). The reason for the bias is the way back-transformation works on skewed random
7 variables and also because LCV is disadvantaged by the presence of outliers with very
8 high values compared to the variance of the field and the value of their neighbors.

9 Given the challenges presented by the informal sampling grid and data distribution,
10 HCE combined with KCDE Gaussian anamorphosis can be considered to give satis-
11 factory and promising results, encouraging further study. In the future, multivariate
12 analysis using co-kriging could be employed and different datasets could be investi-
13 gated to explore the robustness of the HCE with non-Euclidean distances. Another
14 potential suggestion for future studies would be to explore covariance and HCE models
15 with the Spherical manifold (geodesic distance) for ore deposits covering large parts
16 of the Earth's surface or lenticular deposits.

17 **Acknowledgement**

18 The research project is implemented in the framework of H.F.R.I call "Basic research
19 Financing (Horizontal support of all Sciences)" under the National Recovery and
20 Resilience Plan "Greece 2.0" funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU
21 (H.F.R.I. Project Number: 16537).
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

References

- [1] Curriero, F.C.: On the use of non-euclidean distance measures in geostatistics. *Mathematical Geology* **38**, 907–926 (2006)
- [2] Theodoridou, P., Varouchakis, E., Karatzas, G.: Spatial analysis of groundwater levels using fuzzy logic and geostatistical tools. *Journal of Hydrology* **555**, 242–252 (2017)
- [3] BJK Davis, F.C.: Development and evaluation of geostatistical methods for non-euclidean-based spatial covariance matrices. *Mathematical geosciences* (2019)
- [4] Hristopulos, D.T.: Non-separable covariance kernels for spatiotemporal gaussian processes based on a hybrid spectral method and the harmonic oscillator. *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory* (2023)
- [5] Agou, V.D., Varouchakis, E.A., Hristopulos, D.T.: Geostatistical analysis of precipitation in the island of Crete (Greece) based on a sparse monitoring network. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* **191**(353), 1573–2959 (2019) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-019-7462-8>
- [6] Varouchakis, E.A., Guardiola-Albert, C., Karatzas, G.P.: Spatiotemporal geostatistical analysis of groundwater level in aquifer systems of complex hydrogeology. *Water Resources Research* **58**(3), 2021–029988 (2022)
- [7] Ver Hoef, J.M.: Kriging models for linear networks and non-euclidean distances: Cautions and solutions. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* (2018)
- [8] Christakos, G.: *Random Field Models in Earth Sciences*. Academic Press, San Diego (1992)
- [9] Chilès, J.P., Delfiner, P.: *Geostatistics: Modeling Spatial Uncertainty*. Wiley, Hoboken, NJ, USA (2012)
- [10] Hristopulos, D.T.: *Random Fields for Spatial Data Modeling: A Primer for Scientists and Engineers*. Springer, Dordrecht, the Netherlands (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-024-1918-4>
- [11] Pavlides, A., Hristopulos, D.T., Roumpos, C., Agioutantis, Z.: Spatial modeling of lignite energy reserves for exploitation planning and quality control. *Energy* **93**, 1906–1917 (2015) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2015.10.049>
- [12] Pavlides, A., Agou, V.D., Hristopulos, D.T.: Non-parametric kernel-based estimation and simulation of precipitation amount. *Journal of Hydrology* **612**, 127988 (2022)
- [13] Hristopulos, D.T., Pavlides, A., Agou, V.D., Gkafa, P.: Stochastic local interaction model: An alternative to kriging for massive datasets. *Mathematical Geosciences*

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- [14] Agou, V.D., Pavlides, A., Hristopulos, D.T.: Spatial modeling of precipitation based on data-driven warping of gaussian processes. *Entropy* **24**(3), 321 (2022)
 - [15] Pavlides, A., Varouchakis, E., Hristopulos, D.: Geostatistical analysis of groundwater levels in a mining area with three active mines. *Hydrogeology Journal* **31**(6), 1425–1441 (2023)
 - [16] Ghosh, S.: *Kernel Smoothing: Principles, Methods and Applications*. John Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, NJ, USA (2018)
 - [17] Goovaerts, P.: *Geostatistics for Natural Resources Evaluation*. Oxford University Press, New York (1997)
 - [18] Emery, X., Arroyo, D., Mery, N.: Twenty-two families of multivariate covariance kernels on spheres, with their spectral representations and sufficient validity conditions. *Stochastic Environmental Research and Risk Assessment* **36**(5), 1447–1467 (2022)
 - [19] Bochner, S., Tenenbaum, M., Pollard, H.: *Lectures on Fourier Integrals*. Annals of mathematics studies. Princeton University Press, New Jersey (1959)
 - [20] Graczyk, P.: Cramér theorem on symmetric spaces of noncompact type. *Journal of Theoretical Probability* **7**, 609–613 (1994)
 - [21] Emery, X., Alegría, A., Arroyo, D.: Covariance models and simulation algorithm for stationary vector random fields on spheres crossed with euclidean spaces. *SIAM Journal on Scientific Computing* **43**(5), 3114–3134 (2021)
 - [22] Armstrong, M.: Common problems seen in variograms. *Mathematical Geology* **16**(3), 305–313 (1984)
 - [23] Elogne, S., Hristopulos, D., Varouchakis, E.: An application of Spartan spatial random fields in environmental mapping: focus on automatic mapping capabilities. *Stochastic Environmental Research and Risk Assessment* **22**(5), 633–646 (2008) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00477-007-0167-5>
 - [24] Hristopulos, D.T.: Spartan Gibbs random field models for geostatistical applications. *SIAM Journal of Scientific Computing* **24**(6), 2125–2162 (2003)
 - [25] Hristopulos, D.T., Elogne, S.: Analytic properties and covariance functions of a new class of generalized Gibbs random fields. *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory* **53**(12), 4667–4679 (2007)
 - [26] Hristopulos, D.T., Elogne, S.N.: Computationally efficient spatial interpolators based on spartan spatial random fields. *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing* **57**(9), 3475–3487 (2009) <https://doi.org/10.1109/tsp.2009.2021450>

- 1 [27] Varouchakis, E.A., Hristopulos, D.T.: Improvement of groundwater level predic-
2 tion in sparsely gauged basins using physical laws and local geographic features
3 as auxiliary variables. *Advances in Water Resources* **52**, 34–49 (2013) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advwatres.2012.08.002>
4
- 5 [28] Yaglom, A.M.: *Correlation Theory of Stationary and Related Random Functions,*
6 *Volume I: Basic Results* vol. 131. Springer, Berlin, Germany (1987)
7
- 8 [29] Cressie, N.: *Spatial Statistics.* John Wiley and Sons, New York (1993)
9
- 10 [30] Olea, R.A.: *Geostatistics for Engineers and Earth Scientists.* Springer, New York,
11 NY (2012)
12
- 13 [31] Wackernagel, H.: *Multivariate Geostatistics: an Introduction with Applications.*
14 Springer, Berlin, Germany (2003)
15
- 16 [32] Pavlides, A., Agou, V.D., Hristopulos, D.T.: Non-parametric kernel-based estima-
17 tion and simulation of precipitation amount. *Journal of Hydrology* **612**, 127988
18 (2022) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2022.127988>
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65